

D6.1

Integrated Energy System Model

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About this report

This report presents the methodological and data improvements of the TIMES PanEU energy system model. The aim of the report is to provide a detailed look into the methodological enhancements throughout the project to analyse the role of different factors such as behaviour, pollutants and economy in the European energy transition. The report includes a model documentation for TIMES PanEU and insights from the integration of different functions which emerge through different studies carried out in different WPs at each step within the project.

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About REEEM

REEEM aims to gain a clear and comprehensive understanding of the system-wide implications of energy strategies in support of transitions to a competitive low-carbon EU energy society. This project is developed to address four main objectives: (1) to develop an integrated assessment framework (2) to define pathways towards a low-carbon society and assess their potential implications (3) to bridge the science-policy gap through a clear communication using decision support tools and (4) to ensure transparency in the process.

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1. Introduction

The REEEM project aims to explore -in a systematic manner- system-wide implications of energy strategies towards a low carbon society in the European Union (EU) energy system, according to given objectives and framework outlined in the Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan. The scope of this work includes the analysis of the role of technologies in this transition, the impact of consumer behaviour, the synergies between the air pollution control and decarbonisation paths in the energy system, potential heat savings due to renovation in the buildings, the effects on the economy, effects on security and reliability of supply and the effect of climate change within the system itself. An integrated assessment framework covering all these aspects linked to energy system transitions is required to fulfil this objective. In REEEM, the existing TIMES PanEU, initially developed in the NEEDS project [1] and maintained by the University of Stuttgart, hereafter 'USTUTT', lies at the core of this integrated energy system framework [2] and it is linked to several sectoral modelling tools. In TIMES PanEU, the existing data are improved based on the findings of certain case studies and different assessments performed under the scope of the REEEM project. Furthermore, by soft-link with other tools, new methodological approaches are employed to address the influence of the economy, consumers' behaviours, pollutants in the environment and technological developments on the energy system.

In recent years, different integrated assessment frameworks have been developed in the various studies. Different scenarios around decarbonisation of energy systems in the EU and other regions are analysed to understand impact and outcomes of likely transitions. In [3], to cover the energy system and macroeconomic sector, MESSAGE-MACRO model is developed. The focus in this study is on the factors which affect the energy supply costs calculated in the energy system model. These costs are fed to the macroeconomic model. The aim with this link is to create the consistency between the energy demand and supply curves. Two scenarios are developed to compare the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), energy supply and demand, and energy prices figures after the link is established. In another study, TIAM-WORLD (energy system model) is linked with GEMINI-E3 (general equilibrium model) together with a climate model PLASIM-ENTS, to discuss the impacts of climate change on the energy system with emphasis on heating and cooling sectors [4]. The results of such study show that at the regional level the link between these three models shows a different picture than the one given by the energy system model only, in terms of investments in generation capacity required in the energy system. This, in turn, results in the increase in energy prices, especially due to rising cooling demand due to increasing average temperatures. It is observed that the welfare gains and losses are affected by the energy exports and imports changes. However, the changes in the heating and cooling demands don't have significant impact on economic parameters such as GDP.

Studies, taking into account pollutants in the energy system models, are available in the literature as well. In [5], the methodology is explained to create the link between impact assessment models and energy system models. According to this link, the damage costs caused by the pollutants are calculated in the impact assessment model and they are fed back to the energy system model. The synergy between the environmental taxes on pollutants and different CO₂ mitigation scenarios in Italy are discussed in detail with a scenario analysis in [6]. According to the results, the internalisation of the environmental taxes pushes the system to reduce the air pollutants with the deployment of more efficient technologies.

Implementation of consumer behaviour at different parts of the energy system and its impacts on the energy system modelling are discussed in [7] and [8]. The findings in [7] show that consumers behaviours might decelerate the deployment of mitigation technologies in the heating sector.

First in its kind, the integrated assessment framework developed in this research brings all the above mentioned elements together on a EU scale. Specifically, it soft-links the energy system model with a macroeconomic model and a health impact assessment model, considering the consumer behaviour, technology innovation outlooks and impact of climate change on heating and cooling demand.

In this report, TIMES PanEU model and its developments within REEEM are described in detail, as core of the integrated framework. Additionally, the links with other modelling tools and methodologies are explained and the underlying assumptions exposed, for the overall approach to be reproducible with similar tools. Finally, the key updates, enhancements and data harmonisation processes between all tools are described to provide a comprehensive picture of the inter-disciplinary nature of an integrated modelling framework.

Specifically, in Section 2, the specifications of the existing TIMES PanEU model are given and the relations between different parts of the energy system within the model are clarified. In Section 3, the enhancements of the existing TIMES PanEU model are stated and data exchanges with the other models, establishment of soft-links and methodological advancements within each tool are explained. In Section 4, the key results of preliminary scenario analyses are illustrated to enlighten the insights that such framework can provide.

The development of the integrated modelling framework is in its final phase. Once this ends, the framework will be applied to analyse the implications of EU decarbonisation pathways defined within the project, to derive recommendations and key messages for the transition of the energy system. These recommendations and messages will be given in D1.2. Integrated Impact Assessment Report.

2. Core of the framework: TIMES PanEU model

TIMES PanEU is employed as an energy system optimisation model within the course of the REEEM project to analyse the role of different technologies in transitions towards a low-carbon EU energy system. It is further linked to other tools, studies and methodologies to provide a comprehensive assessment of the social, economic and environmental constraints and impacts within these transitions.

TIMES PanEU is built with the TIMES model generator, which is performed in the modelling environment GAMS. It is a model generator to form bottom-up energy system models with linear programming. It has been developed and maintained within the course of Energy Technology System Analyses Program (ETSAP) by the International Energy Agency (IEA) [10, 11]. The data management system (VEDA-TIMES) is used to create an energy system model [12, 13, 14]. Through this data system, the input data, the structure of the model and all the scenario related information are given to the model and they are converted to mathematical equations. The model aims to minimise the total discounted system cost by taking into account all the costs allocated to the energy system in a given time frame to meet the demand services exogenously given as input [15]. TIMES PanEU covers the European Union countries as well as Norway and Switzerland and each country represents a single region in the model. The modelling horizon spans from 2010 to 2050, split into 5 year-time steps. A year is divided into 12 time-slices, 4-seasonal and 3-day level; day, peak and night. Greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O) are included in the model [16, 17, 18]. The basic structure of the model is called reference energy system (RES). RES includes all relevant energy, material, and emission flows from the primary production to meet the demand of energy services for each region defined in the model [19]. RES of the model (i.e. schematic representation of the real EU energy system) covers the entire energy system, from the supply of resources to the demand services in TIMES PanEU. Figure 1 below shows the interactions taken into account between the different parts of the system and outputs calculated after each step.

Different technologies are modelled to make the interactions possible between the parts of the energy system. To model a technology, parameters such as investment cost, efficiency, variable operation and maintenance cost as well as fixed operation and maintenance cost, fuel cost, emission factors, availability factors are required. For certain technologies, some of the above mentioned parameters might not be necessary. In the case of modelling solar power plant, emission factors and fuel costs are not necessary to determine. On the other hand, all the above mentioned parameters are necessary to define a conventional power plant in the system.

Figure 1: TIMES PanEU Reference Energy System [20].

As the starting point of the energy system is the energy sources, TIMES PanEU commences with the supply sector. In this sector, primary energy sources are modelled according to country potentials and the trade possibilities from the surrounding neighbouring countries. Different cost potential curves are defined for each of the sources such as crude oil, natural gas, coal, lignite etc. The World Energy Outlook 2016 prices [21] and average country mining costs are taken as reference to determine the cost figures. Various bioenergy carriers are included again by taking into account the country potential and the costs allocated. Additionally, other conversion technologies such as refineries, gasification's and Power-to-Gas technologies are part of the model [20].

In the electricity sector, the electricity supply at different voltage levels is modelled through different technologies. In the system, the large central power plants feed to high voltage grid; while decentralised generation such as from PV systems feeds to medium and low voltage grids. The technologies which exist at the start of the modelling period and those considered as future options are classified according to the input fuels and technology type. Therefore, the results are classified according to energy carriers, not by individual power plant. The available hydroelectric technologies according to country potentials and all the other renewable technologies are part of the model as well, as different investment options in the electricity sector. New technologies such as electricity storages, hydrogen technologies and carbon capture and storages (CCS) technologies are also modelled. The availability of certain technologies such as CCS is determined according to expected schedule of the technologies to be commercially available in the market [22, 23, 24]. Centrally supplied district heat of cogeneration plants (CHP) are given as an option to provide both electricity and demand. Power-to-Heat technologies together with heat storages are applied in the public heat supply [22, 25, 23].

The industrial sector is modelled as energy-intensive and non-energy-intensive industries. The energy intensive industries cover the categories iron and steel, aluminium, copper, ammonia, chlorine, cement, lime, flat glass, and paper; whereas the non-energy intensive industries include the categories other non-ferrous metals, other chemical, other non-metallic minerals, food and tobacco and other industries. In this sector, industrial auto producers are also modelled [26]. They are given in Table 1 below with their units. There are two different modelling approaches to model the energy inputs within the industrial sector of TIMES PanEU: the process-oriented and application-oriented modelling. The process-oriented approach is applied to model the energy-intensive industries, while the application-oriented is used for the non-intensive industries. In process-oriented modelling, the demand of certain production goods must be met in terms of physical quantities which is in megaton (Mt). This demand is given exogenously to the model. Different technologies with different technical and economic parameters are available at different production stages to supply demand. The choice of technology is a result of the optimisation according to working principle of the model. This demand is determined exogenously. In contrast to process-oriented modelling, the modelling of non-energy-intensive industries based on energy application types requires different types of useful energy. The demand thus refers to an amount of energy (i.e. in PJ) instead of physical quantities. The useful energy demand of the non-energy-intensive industries is divided into different groups according to the different types of application of industrial energy use. These include thermal applications (space heating, hot water, process heat, steam), electric motor applications (pumps, compressed air, fans, refrigeration, other motor applications) and other applications such as lighting, electrochemical conversion processes and other applications. The starting point for this modelling is again the results of the analysis of the industrial sector. To satisfy the demand for useful energy, the model again has different processes with different efficiencies and costs at its disposal. For example, boiler plants or industrial CHP, each based on different fuels, are available for heat supply [26].

Table 1: Industry Sectors and Units

Category	Sector	Unit
Energy Intensive	Iron & Steel	Mt
Energy Intensive	Aluminium	Mt
Energy Intensive	Copper	Mt
Energy Intensive	Ammonia	Mt
Energy Intensive	Chlorine	Mt
Energy Intensive	Cement	Mt
Energy Intensive	Lime	Mt
Energy Intensive	Flat Glass	Mt
Energy Intensive	Paper	Mt
Non-Energy Intensive	Other non-ferrous metals	PJ
Non-Energy Intensive	Other chemicals	PJ
Non-Energy Intensive	Other non-metallic minerals	PJ
Non-Energy Intensive	Food and Tobacco	PJ
Non-Energy Intensive	Other Industries	PJ

In the household, commercial and agriculture segment, the energy service demands are distinguished according to different sectors. Various technologies, aggregated according to technology type and energy carrier, are implemented to provide the energy service demands. There is a further disaggregation in household and commercial energy service demands. The service demand categories in residential and commercial are given in Table 2 below. The process to supply the agriculture demand is defined as one general process. The underlying assumptions of the existing demand figures in TIMES PanEU are consistent with the socio-demographic assumptions of the EU Reference Scenario [27].

Table 2: Service Demand in Residential and Commercial sectors in TIMES PanEU

Residential (PJ)	Commercial (PJ)
Space Heating Single Urban Houses	Space Heating Small
Space Heating Single Rural Houses	Space Heating Large
Space Heating Multi Family Houses	Space Cooling Small
Water Heating Single Urban Houses	Space Cooling Large
Water Heating Single Rural Houses	Lighting
Water Heating Multi Family Houses	Cooking
Space Cooling Single Urban Houses	Refrigeration
Space Cooling Single Rural Houses	Public Lighting
Space Cooling Multi Family Houses	Other Electric
Lighting	Other Energy
Cooking	
Refrigeration	
Cloth Washing	
Cloth Drying	
Dish Washing	
Other Electric	
Other Energy	

The transport sector is also disaggregated according to transportation mode: car, bus, motorcycle, passenger train, freight, air traffic (external and internal) and navigation categories. The passenger transport is modelled in the unit of Pkm (Passenger-km); while the freight is modelled in Tkm (Ton-km) as given in Table 3 below. Different vehicles technologies based on the different energy carriers are modelled for each demand category mentioned above. Hybrid technologies are available in the existing structure as mitigation technologies together with electrical vehicles.

Table 3: Transport Service Demand

Demand	Unit
Road Car Short Distance	Million_Pkm
Road Car Long Distance	Million_Pkm
Road Freight	Million_Pkm
Road Bus Urban	Million_Pkm
Road Bus Intercity	Million_Pkm
Road Moto	Million_Pkm
Rail Freight	Million_Tkm
Rail Passenger Light	Million_Pkm
Rail Passenger Heavy	Million_Pkm
Navigation Generic Bunker	PJ
Aviation Generic	PJ
Aviation International intra EU	PJ
Aviation International extra EU	PJ

3. Development of the Integrated Modelling Framework

The REEEM project aims to develop comprehensive understanding of the implications of the European energy transition towards to a low carbon society. Therefore, one of the objectives of the project is to develop an integrated assessment framework. For this purpose, the existing TIMES PanEU energy system model is linked to other tools and models and further improved.

The resulting integrated assessment framework assesses amongst others:

- economic impacts of the transitions (in terms of competitiveness, GDP, job creation, vulnerability of final consumers),
- health impacts in the society due to pollutants,
- accelerating or inertial effects due to consumer behaviours,
- technology innovation outlooks,
- impact of climate on heating and cooling demands and
- impacts of heat savings in the residential.

The links between different tools which allow for such assessment and their integration within the structure of the REEEM project are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Linking TIMES PanEU with other models and case studies

As seen in Figure 2, TIMES PanEU is centred in REEEM project and exchanges inputs and outputs with several other models and tools. Some of these models are on the EU scale like TIMES PanEU. Therefore, they complement the assessment made by TIMES PanEU for the entire EU, integrating economic, environmental and technological dimensions. Other models are on regional or local scale. Some of these extrapolate information to the EU scale, thereby working like the former. Some exchange information only for the region or city they focus on, thereby working mostly as a calibration tool for TIMES PanEU.

To ease the data exchange, input and output tables are created for each model or tool. These tables are imported to the REEEM Pathway Database. Detailed information about the data can be found in D8.2 REEEM Data Management Plan (DMP) [28]. Different tools utilise different output data from or feed different inputs to the results of TIMES PanEU.

3.1. Harmonisation of inputs between TIMES PanEU and the REEEM Stakeholder Engagement Model OSeMBE

In the REEEM Project, in parallel with the Integrated Modelling Framework, a Stakeholder Engagement Model is created. The latter is meant to represent in a simplified fashion the dynamics occurring in the Integrated Modelling Framework, in terms of roles of technologies and their impact in transition pathways towards a low-carbon EU society. The Engagement Model also feeds the REEEM Energy System Learning Simulation (or REEEM Game), which represents an interface for energy experts and non-experts to look into sample dynamics of the decarbonisation within a ‘serious game setting’. The Stakeholder Engagement Model is fully open source, both in its structure and the datasets it employs. A detailed description of the OSeMBE model can be found in D7.3 OSeMBE [29], whereas the full dataset, metadata and executables can be found on REEEM.org.

Since OSeMBE is meant to represent in a simplified fashion the dynamics implied in the Integrated Modelling Framework and its structure is comparable with the one of TIMES PanEU (though much more aggregated), key techno-economic input data of OSeMBE and TIMES PanEU were harmonised. The harmonisation had a double purpose: 1) the Engagement Model was to be aligned with the Integrated Modelling Framework; 2) selected input data of the Integrated Modelling Framework could be updated and/or replaced with open data sets.

The first step in the harmonisation is a comparison of the technologies modelled in the two models. Since TIMES Pan-EU represents the European energy system in higher more detail than OSeMBE, the task is to identify which technologies in TIMES Pan-EU correspond to which technologies in OSeMBE. After the matching of the technologies is completed, the input data is compared to identify potential discrepancies and to align these discrepancies. In OSeMBE, most technology characteristics are taken from the Energy Technology Reference Indicator (ETRI) projections for 2010-2050 [30]. To keep these data consistent, the technologies that are defined based on data from this report are not changed. However, for technologies that are not covered by the ETRI report other sources are used, e.g. IEA World Energy Outlook 2014 [31]. For combined heat and power plants using natural gas as a fuel and for steam cycle power plant running on coal the technology characteristics are not in line with the TIMES Pan-EU data. Therefore, the TIMES Pan-EU data for these technologies are adopted for OSeMBE. On the other hand, the efficiency of geothermal power plants in TIMES Pan-EU is adjusted according to the ETRI data used in OSeMBE.

The harmonisation of the technology characteristics between TIMES Pan-EU and OSeMBE is of high relevance to increase the comparability of the results of two models. This is important since the stakeholder engagement model aims to replicate the general dynamics of TIMES Pan-EU in a simplified way.

3.2. Integration of technology innovation (Link with WP2)

As the role of technologies is one of the focus points in the integrated assessment of the REEEM project, one key dimension to it is technological innovation. This is assessed through different stages:

- Collection of views on innovation for selected families of technologies by experts within the network of InnoEnergy's industrial partners and literature;
- Inclusion of such views as quantitative information in the TIMES PanEU model;
- Detailed modelling of the technology learning process.

The first point results in the elaboration of three Technology and Innovation Roadmaps, highlighting the impact of selected mitigation technologies in the transition towards a low-carbon energy system. The Roadmaps are complemented by Innovation Readiness Level reports, which assess the maturity of technologies beyond the traditional metric of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL). These outcomes are widely documented in [32, 33].

The second point results in a soft-link between the semi-quantitative assessment of the above point and the TIMES PanEU model. Here, the innovation outlooks of the selected technologies are turned into key techno-economic parameters fed as inputs to the TIMES framework. The procedure is described below in detail.

The third point results in a deeper model re-structuring, operated according to methodology, exogenously modeling, mentioned in [34].

3.2.1 Renewable technologies

One Technology and Innovation Roadmap focuses on renewable technologies in the electricity market, as they will be key in the low-carbon transition and they still exhibit high innovation and/or deployment potential in many Member States. The roadmap describes expected improvements in terms of cost reductions and annual energy production. Among the renewable technologies, priority is given to the following ones [35]:

- Wind power
 - Offshore Wind technology
 - Onshore Wind technology
- Solar PV power
 - Plant Size
 - Rooftop installations
- Ocean Power
 - Tidal
 - Wave

Part of the roadmap is dedicated to turning the market outlook of such technologies into numerical inputs for TIMES PanEU. The market outlook is characterised by high uncertainty, so the final numerical inputs are just one of many potential sets and they depend on the overall narrative of the specific transition under evaluation. To define a technology in TIMES PanEU belonging to the above classification, certain technology parameters are

required. The given data structure for an offshore wind power technology can be seen as an example in Table 4.

Table 4: Offshore wind power technology parameters [35].

Ex: Offshore wind power 10 MW	2020-2025	2030-2035	2040-2045	2050
Investment cost (EUR/kWh)	2018	1798	1438	1078
Net Annual Energy Production (MWh/yr/MW)	4402	4686	4874	5069
Fixed O&M (EUR/kW)	75	63	47	35
Lifetime	27	30	30	30

The complete data set for the other technologies mentioned above is provided in the second roadmap [35].

As the annual energy production cannot be given as a direct input to the model to define a technology, from these values the availability factors are calculated. In the roadmap, there is only one figure available for each technology which refers to the annual average value for the entire Europe; on the other hand, TIMES PanEU works with 12 time slices and 30 different regions. In TIMES PanEU, the existing availability factors were already disaggregated according to this 12 time slices and 30 region structure. To reflect the improvement in the technology in terms of yearly production, the reference points are provided for the net annual energy production figures in the second roadmap. For the offshore and onshore wind, the reference point is specified as United Kingdom and for solar generation is given as Slovenia [35]. Steps, summarized below, are followed to reflect this technological improvement on the existing availability factors:

- First, the annual availability factors are calculated from the yearly annual energy production figures for these countries.
- For the comparison, from the existing 12 time slice values in TIMES PanEU, annual availability factors are calculated. For this calculation, the share of each time slice in a year is used:

Table 5: Year fractions

	Spring Day	Spring Night	Spring Peak	Summer Day	Summer Night	Summer Peak	Autumn Day	Autumn Night	Autumn Peak	Winter Day	Winter Night	Winter Peak
Year fraction	0.097	0.105	0.009	0.114	0.125	0.010	0.097	0.105	0.009	0.151	0.164	0.014

- The new and existing figures are compared with each other.
- The existing figures are proportionally increased according to the increase on the annual factors.
- This direct proportion is later also reflected on the factors belong to other countries.

The insights are shown from the initial results in Section 4.

3.2.2. Storage technologies

The introduction of renewables investigated above, will most probably increase the need for balancing of intermittent renewables. One of the technology families able to contribute to such goal is storage. Therefore, another roadmap analyses selected storage technologies in the energy transition [36].

The modelling of storages in TIMES differs compared to how other technologies are modelled in TIMES PanEU. Each storage process is defined as three different sub-processes instead of one single process. The first process is determined to convert the energy to the form which can be stored; therefore, the unit for this process GW and the principle of this process is similar to a standard power plant process. The second process is defined to store the energy until the output conversion is required. As the actual energy is stored in this process, the unit is PJ in TIMES PanEU. The third and last process is required to convert the energy from the stored version to the form which could be utilized again at different parts of the energy system and this process has the same working principle of the input conversion process. Therefore, for each battery process three different sets of data required to model those technologies in PanEU.

Figure 3: Modelling of a storage technology.

The data provided within the context of the roadmap covers the following technologies:

- Pumped Hydro Storages
 - Pump Storage Reservoir
 - Pump Storage Reservoir Seasonal
- Compressed Air Energy Storages (CAES)
 - CAES Adiabatic Underground
 - CAES Diabatic Underground
 - CAES Adiabatic Underground
- Batteries
 - Lithium Ion
 - Lead Acid
 - Vanadium Redox

- Nickel Cadmium
- Sodium Sulphur

As mentioned, each of these processes is defined as three different processes in the model. The structure of the data for Li-on storage battery can be seen as an example in the Table 6 and Table 7 below. The expected technological learning is considered in the cost assumptions for the technologies.

Table 6: Lithium Ion Battery-Input/Output technology parameters [9]

Ex: Lithium Ion Battery-Input/Output	2015	2020-2025	2030-2035	2040-2045	2050
Investment cost (EUR/kW)	140	120	100	80	40
Efficiency (%)	1	1	1	1	1
Var. O&M (EUR/kWh)	0	0	0	0	0
Fixed O&M (EUR/kW)	0	0	0	0	0
Lifetime	10	10	10	10	10

Table 7: Lithium Ion Battery-Storage technology parameters [9]

Ex: Lithium Ion Battery-Storage	2015	2020-2025	2030-2035	2040-2045	2050
Investment cost (EUR/kWh)	400	350	300	200	150
Efficiency (%)	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9
Var. O&M (EUR/kWh)	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Fixed O&M (EUR/kWh)	5,6	4,9	4,2	2,8	2,1
Lifetime	10	10	10	10	10

During the modelling practice, existing capacities for those technologies and the country potentials for pumped hydro storages as well as CAES are considered and given as input to the model. As the batteries are not deployed yet at commercial scale, the existing capacities in the base year are not considered.

As TIMES PanEU has 12 times slices in a year, it may be hard to fully capture the capacity deployment for the storages even with the expected cost reduction figures due to the working principle of storages. This limitation of the low temporal resolution model with the application of storages has been already addressed in different studies [37, 23, 25]. Therefore, here it is suggested that higher temporal resolution is required to better investigate the role of storages. This can be further analysed with a different energy system model or an electricity market model with higher temporal resolution. Although, there is a model, PLEXOS, employed in

REEM with lower temporal resolution focusing on the electricity market model; due to the design and aim of the case study, the storages are also not analyzed further within their scope.

3.2.3. Residential Technologies

Another set of technologies which could contribute to the decarbonisation of the EU economy while limiting the need for balancing intermittent sources are residential technologies, especially focusing on the residential heating, both on large scale (district heating) and individual household scale. Therefore, the last Technology and Innovation Roadmap, yet to be published, focuses on technologies for energy efficiency improvement in residential buildings. They look at foreseen technological developments, especially improvements in COP values of heat pumps according to seasons and heat saving measures.

3.2.3.1. COP values of Heat Pumps

Heat pumps are classified as renewable energy technologies as well as zero emission technologies under certain conditions in Europe. COP values of heat pumps have high dependency on the temperature of the cooling reservoir. Most heat pumps utilise cooling reservoirs with dependency on the seasonal temperatures which makes it important to take the seasonal variation into account. Moreover, the temperatures differ significantly based on the climate therefore country-specific COP values should be adjusted as well.

Within the Roadmap, efficiencies of heat pumps have been adjusted according to seasons. The COP values are calculated utilising Lorentz efficiency equation (It is assumed working with an average range of temperature for the heat pump).

$$COP_{h,Lorentz} = \frac{T_m[K]}{T_m[K] - T_{evap}[K]}$$

By utilising an average representation of the yearly outdoor temperature distribution [38] (above and below ground levels) , spatial heating temperature (35° to 55°C for new and existing buildings, respectively) and hot water temperature (65°C), it is possible to calculate the maximum theoretical COP for the individual countries, using Lorentz equation.

As the maximum theoretical COP does not apply directly into the heat pumps, their individual technical efficiency is calculated based on the Danish Energy Agencies technology catalogue COP values [39] for Danish heat pumps and the calculated maximum theoretical COP for the heat pump in Denmark.

Multiplying the calculated technical efficiency with the country specific maximum theoretical COP provides both country specific COP values calculated seasonally. It is assumed the heat pump technologies are unanimous across EU countries making their technical efficiencies equal. Temperature is thereby the only variable for the country specific COP values. Utilising the national average temperatures, an estimate of COP values is included into the TIMES PanEU framework.

In line with the findings of the third Technology Innovation Roadmap, the modelling of heat pumps in TIMES PanEU is further developed with the implementation of specific efficiency values.

3.2.3.2. Potentials & Cost of heat savings in European energy system

Heating and cooling demands are responsible for half of the EU energy consumption (including waste). Therefore, the reduction of heating and cooling demands in residential buildings by means of energy efficiency measures is one of the priorities of the European Energy Union [40]. The third Technology Innovation Roadmap assesses potentials and costs of heat savings for residential buildings.

Potentials and cost of heat savings for the residential buildings collected in the third Technology Innovation Roadmap are implemented into TIMES PanEU, to provide a model-based assessment of their likely impacts on the EU energy system.

Heat savings in residential buildings are modelled through four parameters in TIMES PanEU:

- Potentials (PJ of annual savings)
- Investment costs (Million Euro/PJ of annual savings)
- Lifetimes (years)
- Discount rate (%)

They are modelled as processes that supply heat according to a fixed profile to satisfy part of the heating demand.

Potentials

Heating demands before renovation actions, after "Usual" and after "Advanced" renovation actions are obtained from TABULA/Episcopo project [41]. The heat saving potentials are defined as difference between heating demands before and after the renovation actions. Therefore, two heat saving potentials are defined for each category of the residential building stock in each of the analysed countries - "Usual" and "Advanced". The potentials are defined as shares (in %) of the heating demand before renovation actions. Possibilities for reduction of domestic hot water demands are not included.

Investment costs

The results of TABULA/Episcopo project include heat savings per element of building element (windows, floors, walls, etc.) for both Usual¹ and Advanced² levels [41]. For the elements whose thermal performances are improved by adding insulation (walls, floors, roofs), the additional level of insulation is calculated from the U-value of the element before and after the renovation measures. For windows, there is no addition of insulation, so the U-value after replacement is used for the calculation of costs.

The Danish values are used as a starting point for renovation costs of each element of the building envelope in EU countries [42, 43, 44], as presented in the Table 8. The renovation costs represent expected average values

¹ "Usual Refurbishment": package of measures for upgrading the thermal envelope and the heat supply system which are commonly realised during renovation

² "Advanced Refurbishment": package of measures for upgrading the thermal envelope and the heat supply system which are usually only realised in very ambitious renovations or research projects

from 2012 to 2050. They are divided into a fixed and variable part. The fixed part corresponds to labour costs, while the variable corresponds to material costs. The applied costs represent "marginal costs", i.e. the costs of heat saving measures if they are done after the end of the lifetime of a specific component.

Table 8: Cost assumptions for Denmark

	Fixed [DKK ³ /m ² of element)	Variable [DKK/(mm*m ² of element)]	Therm. resist. of insulation material [m ² K/W]	Indicative u-value [W/m ² K]
Walls	200	7	0.037	-
Roofs	50	1	0.037	-
Floors	350	0	0.037	-
Window - class C	2500	0	-	1.3
Window - class B	2500	120	-	1.1
Window - class A	2500	240	-	0.9
Window - class A+	2500	360	-	0.7

The variable part of the renovation costs (material costs) is maintained the same for all EU countries. The fixed part (labour costs) per country is calculated by scaling the Danish costs with the GDP per capita of each country relative to Danish GDP per capita.

$$c_i = c_{F,i} + c_{V,i} = c_{F,DK} + c_{V,DK} \cdot k_{i,DK}; k_{i,DK} = \frac{GDP_{pc,i}}{GDP_{pc,DK}}$$

c_i - cost of heat saving measure for an element of building envelope in country i

$c_{F,i}$, $c_{F,DK}$ - fixed part of cost of heat saving measure for an element of building envelope in country i and Denmark, respectively

$c_{V,i}$, $c_{V,DK}$ - variable part of cost of heat saving measure for an element of building envelope in country i and Denmark, respectively

$k_{i,DK}$ - scaling factor between country i and Denmark

$GDP_{pc,i}$, $GDP_{pc,DK}$ - GDP per capita in country i and Denmark, respectively

Lifetimes

Heat saving measures have different lifetimes - 25 years for windows, 35 years for roofs and 40 years for floors and walls. Heat saving measures that are used as inputs to TIMES PanEU are aggregates of heat saving measures. Therefore, their lifetimes are between 25 and 40 years. A conservative approach of using 25 years as the technical

³ DKK is Danish Krone; 1 EUR=7.45 DKK

lifetime for all the heat saving options in TIMES PanEU is adopted. The characterisation of different levels of heat savings with different lifetimes requires further research.

Discount rate

The internal discount rate of TIMES PanEU model (i.e. 5%) is used for discounting the costs over the lifetime. Other discount rates can be defined if conditions of a specific study demand it.

Aggregation of the residential building stock

The inputs to TIMES PanEU are defined for 8 types of residential buildings stock: 4 groups according to construction periods (i.e. before 1920; from 1921 to 1960; from 1961 to 2000; and after 2001) and 2 according to use (i.e. single-family and multi-family).

The TABULA/Episcopo dataset did not include data for all the EU countries. Therefore, potentials (in % of heating demand in the base year) and costs (in EUR/kWh) for the countries with missing data were calculated as average values of similar EU countries for which the data existed. Countries are considered similar if they have a similar economy and similar climate. The list of countries considered similar available in the Table 9.

Table 9: Countries for which potential and cost of heat savings were calculated based on similar countries

Country	Proxy 1	Proxy 2
Croatia	Serbia	Slovenia
Estonia	Poland	Sweden
Finland	Sweden	Norway
Latvia	Poland	Sweden
Lithuania	Poland	Sweden
Luxemburg	Belgium	The Netherlands
Malta	Cyprus	Italy
Portugal	Estonia	
Romania	Hungary	Bulgaria
Slovakia	Hungary	Czech Republic

Not all construction periods contribute equally to the heat savings potentials (for example, buildings between 1920 and 1960 contribute more to the heat savings potential than buildings between 1961 and 2000). The weights are assigned to each of the age groups based on the heated area.

3.3. Integration of externalities & damage costs (Link with WP5)

The European Union has targets to reduce energy related CO₂ emissions but there is no single EU strategy to reduce air pollutions and their health impacts [45]. The targets to reduce pollutions are set at the national level and the responsibility belongs to national governments to achieve.

GHG and air pollutants result mainly from the combustion of fossil fuels in the energy system. Therefore, the synergies between GHG reduction targets and air pollution mitigation policies should be addressed in the transition towards to a low carbon EU society. Such synergies may reduce health impacts of emissions, especially in cities and densely populated areas. Additionally, they may bring savings on health costs. These costs reflect the monetary loss in welfare. This part of the REEEM work aims at illuminating cause-effect relationships between energy sector emissions and health costs for the citizens.

To analyse such interaction and assess the health impacts from energy-related emissions, a link between the TIMES PanEU energy system model and the health impact assessment model EcoSense is created. Such a link is already analysed in the course of NEEDS project [1] and within the REEEM work is further developed. This link is shown schematically in Figure 4, expanding from Figure 2.

Figure 4: The link between TIMES PanEU and EcoSense

EcoSense is an integrated assessment model which estimates health and environmental impacts caused by air pollutants. The main focus of the model is to analyse the benefits from the different emission reduction scenarios in Europe through the time horizon up to 2050. It links the changes in emissions of several air pollutants on country level to different health outcomes on grid level. To create such links, it considers the dispersion of the emissions, their chemical transformation and the population density as well as background disease rates of different health outcomes [46, 47]. The model has an original grid resolution of 0.25° x 0.5°. For calculating unit cost factors, the results on grid level are aggregated to country specific cost factors following the “polluter pays” principle, i.e. all damages across the whole domain are allocated to the country from which the emissions are originating. This is done separately for each pollutant and each source country. The exact calculation of unit cost factors is described in the forthcoming deliverable D5.2.

To realise the link between TIMES PanEU and EcoSense, the steps below are followed:

- The existing emission coefficients of the pollutants SO₂, NO_x, CO, NMVOC, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, (kt/PJ), are updated in TIMES PanEU. The coefficients are disaggregated according to sectors, regions and

technology types in the energy system. The sources and methodology are explained detailed in D5.2., which is yet to be published.

- Based on those coefficients, TIMES PanEU provides to EcoSense total emission figures (kt) for each pollutant according to different sectors from the results of the Base Pathway [9] defined in the project.
- By utilising the data given from TIMES PanEU, EcoSense calculates the unit health damage costs (€/kg) of the pollutants. These are disaggregated according to different pollutants without sectoral decomposition and fed back to TIMES PanEU. The assumptions and methodology to calculate the unit damage costs are explained in REEEM Deliverable D5.2, yet to be published.
- The unit damage costs are implemented and the total damage costs are calculated in the model according to the following equations [48]:

$$DAM (EM) = \alpha * EM^{(\beta+1)}$$

where:

- EM (kt) is the emission in the current period
- DAM (EUR/kt) is the damage cost in the current period
- $\beta \geq 0$ is the elasticity of the marginal damage cost to amount of emissions
- $\alpha > 0$ is a calibrating parameter, which may be obtained from dose-response studies that allow the computation of the marginal damage cost per unit of emission at some reference level of emissions

If the marginal cost at the reference level MC_0 is denoted, the following holds:

- $MC_0 = \alpha * (\beta+1) * EM_0^{(\beta)}$ which is calculated by EcoSense according to the link between the models.
 - $\beta=0$ as elasticity factor is not considered in the calculation
 - $DAM (EM) = (MC_0 * (EM^{(\beta+1)} / ((\beta+1) * EM_0^{(\beta)})))$
- These cost factors are introduced into the model starting from 2020 as the base year of the model 2015 and these costs are not taken into account in the system design in reality.
 - As the cost factors will be added into the energy system model's optimisation function to approximate a policy decision to have a tax on externalities, it is assumed they would be 'phased in' gradually and only half costs accounted in 2020 since in real life they are not taken into account at present. This also matched with 5-year model structure.
 - From 2030 on, the calculated unit damage cost (€/kg) values by EcoSense are employed directly in the model. This implementation can be considered as step-wise introduction with this structure.
 - The cost figures are calculated for each region in TIMES PanEU according to milestone years.

The range of those cost figures is shown in Table 10 below.

Table 10: Unit cost factors of air pollutants as implemented in TIMES PanEU

€/kg	NH3	NOX	PM2.5	PM10	SO2	NMVOC
2020	8.62 (1.41;22.13)	4.48 (0.55;10.72)	25.94 (3.99;48.88)	0.90 (0.14;1.97)	10.54 (2.20;28.14)	1.19 (0.31;2.86)
2030	17.26 (2.95;44.2)	8.98 (1.10;21.63)	52.13 (8.03;99.35)	1.80 (0.28;3.99)	21.19 (4.43;56.92)	2.39 (0.64;5.61)
2040	16.92 (3.02;42.79)	8.83 (1.09;21.29)	51.26 (7.94;97.70)	1.78 (0.28;4.01)	20.85 (4.37;56.00)	2.35 (0.63;5.61)
2050	16.57 (3.09;41.41)	8.68 (1.08;20.94)	50.39 (7.84;96.04)	1.77 (0.28;4.04)	20.51 (4.30;55.08)	2.31 (0.63;5.51)

In Ecosense, the function to calculate the unit damage cost factors according to sectoral disaggregation is not available yet.

The health damage costs can be used for two types of assessments in energy system modeling:

- To provide an exogenous economic evaluation of the health damages by the energy system, without any feedback to the cost optimisation function (ex-post);
- To study how the optimal energy supply mix would change, if health damage costs were to be internalised, as part of the cost optimisation function (ex-ante). This would correspond to a scenario where a taxation is introduced on emissions, equivalent to the health damage the emissions are likely to cause.

Both types of assessment are carried out and to the REEEM Base Pathway. The insights are provided in Section 4.

No iteration between TIMES PanEU and EcoSense is required for the linkage between two models. Due to the linear relationship between the total damage costs and the total emissions to calculate the damage costs in EcoSense, the unit costs are independent from the amount of emissions. The calculation of the emission factors and unit costs reflect the policies in the Clean Air Policy Package [45]. According to these policies and regulations, the calculations are independent from different climate mitigation policies. This means that the values are scenario independent as well.

These factors will be later recalculated by another impact assessment model, EVA, to have the sectoral disaggregation and be implemented in TIMES PanEU for sensitivity analyses.

3.4. Integration with other case studies

Several case studies are developed in REEEM, to zoom in specific issues related with the deep decarbonisation of the EU energy system, visible on a regional and local scale, but hardly noticed on the EU scale. Two of these case studies focus on energy security and reliability of supply.

The first one is a regional energy security case study (REEEM T6.4) focusing on the Baltic region. Due to the dependency on oil and coal imports from Russia, there is an energy security concern in the region. The case study is based on a detailed energy system model of the Baltics, including Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Finland and developed in MESSAGE framework.

The model is used in REEEM to assess opportunities and threats of the decarbonisation of the EU energy system for the Baltics and thereby assist national energy planning processes. Therefore, the model was fed with results from the Integrated Modelling Framework, as applied to the REEEM Pathways [9]. Specifically, the following results of the TIMES PanEU energy system model were incorporated in the regional model:

- The share of renewable energy in the electricity production;
- The share of renewable energy in the district heat production;
- The share of renewable energy in primary energy consumption;
- CO₂ prices resulted in TIMES PanEU.

The methodologies and insights from the case study are described in depth in REEEM D6.2 – Regional Energy Security Case Study report.

The second case study (REEEM T6.4) focuses on grid and dispatch operational challenges in a decarbonised EU. For a detailed representation, it once again zooms into a more specific time period and region: it looks at the electricity market in Balkan countries (Bulgaria, Croatia, Romania, Slovenia and Hungary) in 2030, with hourly temporal resolution. The aim of the case study is specifically to verify the feasibility of dispatch of the EU-wide energy mix resulting from the Integrated Modelling Framework. To fulfil the objective, another soft-link is created between the energy system model, TIMES PanEU, and an electricity market model built in PLEXOS. With an intent and a process similar to the one of the previous case study, the following input and output data of TIMES PanEU is used as input in PLEXOS:

- Electricity generation capacities;
- Electricity demand calculated from the electricity consumption in each sector in TIMES PanEU;
- Electricity exchange capacities;
- Variable operation and maintenance cost;
- Fuel and CO₂ emission prices;
- Electricity generation;
- Heat demand.

The detailed information from this case study can be found in REEEM D6.3 – Grid and Dispatch Case Study report.

During the process, also part of the input data of TIMES PanEU model related to the Baltic and Balkan regions were updated with inputs from the case studies. These improvements are listed in Table 11 below.

Table 11: Data updates in TIMES PanEU model

Country	REEEM Task	Input
Bulgaria	T6.4 – Grid & Dispatch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The installed capacities of lignite, coal, nuclear and hydro are updated in the base year and 2015 • Decommissioning curves of these power plants are aligned according to the given information. • The energy balance is also calibrated again based on the updated data affiliated with power plants.
Croatia	T6.4 – Grid & Dispatch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing capacities for hydro, coal and natural gas as well as the decommissioning curves of those technologies are updated. • The capacity factors are also improved for the technologies in line with the preliminary results from the grid and Dispatch case study. • Planned commissioning capacities of Coal, Hydro and CHP are implemented as fixed capacities to be built.
Hungary	T6.4 – Grid & Dispatch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calibration for the base year capacities according to technology types is also carried out. • The nuclear capacity deployment is implemented according to the commissioning of the new units and the available hydro potential in the country is calibrated based on the data provided
Slovenia	T6.4 – Grid & Dispatch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The hydro potential calibration is applied to reflect the available potential. • Hydro pumped storage capacity in 2015 updated. • Decommissioning curve for the existing nuclear power plant in the country is altered based on the given data.
Romania	T6.4 – Grid & Dispatch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wind and solar technology capacities in 2015 calibrated • Base year capacities for coal, oil, gas, lignite and CHP capacities are updated with the decommissioning curves. • The capacity factor of hydro power plant is improved.
Estonia	T6.4 – Regional energy security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calibration for the base year capacities according to technology types is carried out.
Finland	T6.4 – Regional energy security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data comparison is carried out • Wind capacity is updated accordingly.
Latvia	T6.4 – Regional energy security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Base year capacities of CHP and hydro plants are calibrated along with the decommissioning curves.
Lithuania	T6.4 – Regional energy security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Base year capacities calibrated for CHP plants.

As a last step in this part of the work, the exchange capacities for the electricity trade between the countries are calibrated along with the actual exchange data in 2015 [49]. The intended extensions for those capacities according to ENTSO-E reports are implemented for the time horizon covered by the TIMES PanEU model [50].

The two case studies described above show the importance of a precise representation of the current energy system structure and the potential constraints in future infrastructure investments, for assessing the implications of decarbonisation in sub-regions. Therefore, the harmonisation of inputs between them and TIMES PanEU energy system model is believed to represent one first step into the enrichment of the EU model with local information able to illuminate local dynamics previously neglected. Such approach should be extended in the future to other EU regions.

The modelling work is currently ongoing in the above mentioned case studies. Their results will be compared with the relevant TIMES PanEU results and the relevant messages and recommendations will be given from the model links in D1.2. Integrated Impact Assessment Report.

Apart from the above mentioned case studies, other studies in REEEM analyse the energy transition in the EU from different perspectives. TIMES PanEU results are employed in those as well with a similar intent.

One case study in REEEM focuses on district heating in Helsinki region, Kaunas and Warsaw. The main goal of the study is to examine what implications the decarbonisation of the wider EU energy system could have on the deployment of city-level DH systems and related energy prices. Therefore, once again a soft-link is created between TIMES PanEU model and the model used in the specific case study, where outputs of the former are fed as inputs to the latter. CO₂ prices and changes in heat and electricity generation capacities resulting from TIMES PanEU are used as input to the case study model. The case study is described detailed in [51].

In WP4, a study is carried out, aiming to assess distributional impacts of the decarbonisation and highlight the degree of vulnerability of final consumers and industries. The following data is fed to a model specifically used for such assessment (InVEST) from the results of TIMES PanEU:

- Electricity production from Coal and Lignite;
- Final energy consumption of the residential according to fuel and demand types;
- Final energy consumption of the industry according to subsectors and fuel type;
- Fixed O&M costs in residential according to fuel and demand types;
- Investments costs in residential according to fuel and demand types;
- Variable O&M costs in residential according to fuel and demand types.

Finally, life cycle analyses (REEEM T5.3) are carried out in WP5, to assess the life cycle impacts and resource use by technologies which will have key roles in the transition to a low-carbon EU energy system and pinpoint potential hot spots of critical materials scarcity. Accordingly, the life cycle simulations analyse the technology mix resulting from the pathways assessed through the Integrated Modelling Framework. Specifically, they take as inputs the following outputs of the TIMES PanEU model:

- Person and ton kilometres according to different vehicle technologies and railways;
- Fuel inputs to different vehicle categories and transport modes;
- Electricity generation capacities including CHPs;
- Electricity generation;

- Heat production;
- Net electricity consumption in each sector;
- Final energy consumption according to energy carriers in each sector;
- Electricity exchange.

These studies will be finalised at the end of the project.

3.5. Integration of behavioural insights from survey results (Link with WP4)

It is widely discussed that often energy system modelling exercises fail to represent the barriers and enablers to change coming from the society. The society is the ultimate recipient of any change happening in the energy system. It is both affected by it, as changes in the mix could reflect into changes in prices, thereby affordability. At the same time, it affects the transition, as it can introduce inertial effects which can accelerate it or slow it down. No discussion over a rapid transition to a low-carbon society can be made without taking consumers into account.

In the REEEM project, surveys were carried out in the United Kingdom, Croatia and Finland, to understand the consumer preferences on domestic heating systems and privately owned vehicles in the next replacement period of their existing technology. Different questions are formulated to understand the main drivers for their choices, among lifestyle, income level, attitudes and other social factors. To find out the drivers which affect the decision making, discrete choice modelling is employed. According to the results of the discrete choice model, different drivers affect the decision making in different countries and these drivers are not identical for the heating and transport choices [52]. The complete set of findings of the surveys is presented in [53].

It may be difficult to implement all discrete findings of surveys in three countries into a EU-scale energy model and have a detailed representation of consumers' behaviours. However, selected insights are included in the TIMES PanEU framework, to enrich it with a set of potential inertial effects coming from consumer's habits and choices on new technologies.

One of the key findings is that consumers often choose as new heating system or vehicle the same they used to own. However, this finding cannot be directly implemented in the TIMES PanEU model, due to the linear optimisation structure in the objective function. Another factor influencing the choice of heating system across all the surveyed countries seems to be the housing type. Therefore, this factor is chosen as a proxy in all the countries subject to the survey for the heating system choice in the next decision period for the existing technologies. As in TIMES PanEU space heating demand is disaggregated based on the housing types (i.e. single, rural and multi-family), this insight is implemented into the model for the surveyed countries. For the implementation, the ratios for consumers' preferences for future purchase decisions with respect to 2015 are calculated according to the housing types. The results of these calculations can be seen in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Heat technology choices according to house types in UK, FI &HR

The share of the energy carriers in final energy consumption in the residential sector of each country is calibrated according to the updated statistics in Eurostat for 2015 [54]. The existing technology choices in the current model are aggregated to be in line with the categories determined according to survey results. As a next step after the technology classification, fixed constraints are implemented for the new capacities of the heating technologies based on the house type to reflect the results in the graphs above. However, these results only reflect the consumer choices for immediate future decisions on heating technologies which means in 2020. These constraints are relaxed after 2020 through the time horizon, to give the chance for the higher acceptance of the new technology in the future.

As mentioned briefly, the existing system in the household is influential for the choice of the following heating system. To reflect this finding in the model, for the countries not subject to the survey, the capacity share of the technologies in terms of energy carriers is calculated based on the housing type (i.e. multi-family, single rural and single urban), in 2015. The following categories of the heating systems are determined for all the three housing types:

- District heating
- Electricity
- Gas
- Heat Pump
- Oil
- Solid

After this calculation, as upper and lower bounds for the next capacity deployment of the heating technology respect to 2015, 5% ranges are implemented. This means that if in a specific country the share of gas-fired

technologies in heating systems was 20% in 2015, the capacity share of the gas-fired technologies in 2020 is bounded as maximum 25% and minimum 15%. These constraints are released over time (as done for the surveyed countries), in order to give enough flexibility in the long term.

The initial comparison between the model results with and without behavioural insights for the heating technologies shows that the behaviour is mainly in line with cost-optimisation decisions made with perfect foresight.

As explained above, survey results are implemented to affect the decision making in the short term as the results of the survey reflect only the decisions of consumers for the next time they need to choose a new heating system. Considering the mitigation technologies become competitive and GHG reductions targets more ambitious after 2030, no major differences result with this improvement, compared to the case where behaviour is not accounted for. It is proven that decisional patterns mainly rely on cost factors.

As far as transport technologies are concerned, the only common driver of technology choice across the countries appears to be cost [52, 53]. The current modelling approach of TIMES PanEU already takes cost into account. Therefore, any additional user constraints or implementation are not realized in this part of the energy system.

3.6. Effect of the Heating & Cooling degree days` change on Heating & Cooling Demand

Climate change can have a significant effect on heating/cooling demand. According to the Danish experience, every 1°C increase reduces the heating demand by 7%. The original analysis of the future changes in heating and cooling demand in Europe is documented in [55]. In this section, the steps to implement the changes on the heating/cooling demand in TIMES PanEU are explained.

In order to reflect the effect of climate change on future heating and cooling demands across the EU, data from CORDEX database for RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 are used [56]. The utilised data comprised daily minimum, maximum and mean temperatures for a historical period (1995-2005) and the modelled period (2006-2055) for the whole EU from several combinations of regional and global climate models (Table 12).

Table 12: Combinations of regional and global climate models

Regional climate model	Driving global climate model	Combined short name	Organisation
CCLM4	EC-EARTH	CCLM4_EC	CLM community
HIRHAM5	EC-EARTH	HIRHAM5_EC	Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)
RACMO22	EC-EARTH	RACMO22_EC	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut (KNMI)
RACMO22	HADGEM2	RACMO22_HAD	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut (KNMI)
REMO2009	MPI-ESM-LR	REMO2009_MPI	Max Planck Institute (MPI)
RCA4	EC-EARTH	RCA4_EC	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)
RCA4	HADGEM2	RCA4_HAD	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)
RCA4	MPI-ESM-LR	RCA4_MPI	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)

Based on the data from the climate models, the future heating degree days (HDD) and cooling degree days (CDD) were calculated using equations 1-4 [57] with 12.5 km resolution (i.e. corresponding to the resolution of the temperature data from the CORDEX database). Heating degree days are calculated during the cold period from fall to spring (Oct 1 to March 31 – 183 days in non-leap years) and cooling degree days in the warm period (Apr 1 to Sep 30 – 182 days). To account for the variability between years and seasons, 10-year averages for daily minimum, maximum and mean temperatures are used in the calculations.

$$HDD_{i,t} = \begin{cases} \frac{T_{b,h} - T_{M,i,t}}{2} - \frac{T_{X,i,t} - T_{b,h}}{4} \\ \frac{T_{b,h} - T_{N,i,t}}{4} \\ 0 \end{cases} \text{ if } \begin{cases} T_{b,h} \geq T_{X,i,t} \\ T_{M,i,t} \leq T_{b,h} < T_{X,i,t} \\ T_{N,i,t} \leq T_{b,h} < T_{M,i,t} \\ T_{b,h} \leq T_{N,i,t} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$HDD_{i,y} = \sum_{t=1,t \in y}^{183} HDD_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

$$CDD_{i,t} = \begin{cases} 0 \\ \frac{T_{X,i,t} - T_{b,c}}{4} \\ \frac{T_{X,i,t} - T_{b,c}}{2} - \frac{T_{b,c} - T_{N,i,t}}{4} \\ T_{M,i,t} - T_{b,c} \end{cases} \text{ if } \begin{cases} T_{b,c} \geq T_{X,i,t} \\ T_{M,i,t} \leq T_{b,c} < T_{X,i,t} \\ T_{N,i,t} \leq T_{b,c} < T_{M,i,t} \\ T_{b,c} \leq T_{N,i,t} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$CDD_{i,y} = \sum_{t=1,t \in y}^{182} CDD_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

where:

$T_{b,h} = 15.5^\circ\text{C}$ – Base temperature for calculation of HDD

$T_{b,c} = 22^\circ\text{C}$ – Base temperature for calculation of CDD

$T_{M,i,t}$ - Mean temperature in cell i in day t

$T_{X,i,t}$ - Maximal temperature in cell i in day t

$T_{N,i,t}$ - Minimal temperature in cell i in day t

$HDD_{i,t}, CDD_{i,t}$ – HDD and CDD in cell i and day t

$CDD_{i,y}, CDD_{i,y}$ - HDD and CDD in cell i and year y

Weighing HDD and CDD

After calculating HDD and CDDs for every cell in EU in 5-year steps between 2010 and 2050, weights were applied to account for population density [58] as a measure for demand rates.

The weights of the cells were calculated as follows:

$$w_i = \frac{\sum_{j \in i} P_{i,j}}{P_k} \quad (5)$$

Where:

w_i – weight of 12.5x12.5 km cell i

$P_{i,j}$ – Population of 1x1 km cell which belongs to cell j and 12.5x12.5 km cell i

P_k – Population of country k

i - 12.5x12.5 km cell

j – 1x1 km cell

k – EU countries

The weights were applied and the HDDs and CDDs were aggregated to the national level, for every country k :

$$HDD_k = \sum_{i \in k} HDD_i \cdot w_i \quad (6)$$

$$CDD_k = \sum_{i \in k} CDD_i \cdot w_i \quad (7)$$

The ratios of space heating/cooling demands in different years should correspond to the ratios between HDDs/CDDs in the same years. These ratios (between the model base year and future years) could be applied to space heating/cooling demand in TIMES-PanEU in 2010 to obtain future values. However in TIMES PanEU, heating and cooling demand values throughout the model horizon are projected by taking into account population development, economic growth according to EU reference scenario [27], requirement of space heating per capita and demolishing rates for the existing buildings based on 2010 values (except for 2015 values which are driven according to statics). The projection does not include any correction for future climate, therefore the ratios are applied to the values in the corresponding years instead of 2010.

This approach is not applicable for countries that do not have existing cooling or heating demand in 2010. This limitation should be addressed in the future work.

3.7. Economic impacts of the energy transition (Link with WP3)

An energy transition implying deep fuel shifts and significant investments towards decarbonisation is likely to carry impacts on economies, in terms of GDP growth, job market, gains or losses in competitiveness, etc. Winners and losers may arise among the EU Member States. Studying these dynamics is key to understanding opportunities and threats of the decarbonisation of the energy system. In the REEEM project, the interactions between economy and specific policy instruments (such as emission reduction targets) or technology developments in the energy system are analysed in a specific work package, WP3.

This analysis is carried out with NEWAGE, a top-down, recursive dynamic general equilibrium model which finds the pare to point between different players in the economy [59]. NEWAGE has a higher degree of detail in the electricity sector than in other sectors.

However, as much as the development of the energy sector has implications for the whole economy, conversely the whole economy (especially changes in fuel prices, population and GDP growth) has impacts on the demand-supply equilibrium in the energy sector. To capture these cross-impact, a bi-directional, iterative link is established in REEEM between NEWAGE and the energy system model TIMES PanEU.

The main objective of this linkage is to assess the effect of economic variations such as GDP development and sectoral growth on energy demand in TIMES PanEU and feed the changes in the electricity supply technology mix and in the energy costs back into NEWAGE. This is why the link between the two models is iterative. The linkage between the two models is intended in REEEM as the last step to complete the integrated assessment model structure, where all the other developments are already taken into account. After the completion of the last step, the full framework is ready for the analysis of the REEEM pathways.

Figure 6: The link between TIMES PanEU & NEWAGE

The above mentioned data exchange between the two models is summarised in Figure 6, extracting from Figure 2. Before initiating the iteration process, both models are calibrated and the steps are followed:

- As a first step, electricity mix and industrial demand figures in the existing model structure of TIMES PanEU are adjusted to recently updated statistical available data for 2015 [27].

- Secondly, TIMES PanEU provides the results of the EU Reference Scenario [27] for calibration of NEWAGE. This scenario is required for NEWAGE to determine the reference development of the economic growth in different sectors and GDP.
- After the calibration of NEWAGE according to EU Reference Scenario, NEWAGE is re-calibrated and run based on the results of the Base Pathway [9] developed in the REEEM project. As the aim is to take into account all the different drivers in the energy system, the results from the version of the Base Pathway with the damage costs included in the optimisation function (exante) are employed in this run.
- In this structure, the underlying assumptions of the existing demand figures in TIMES PanEU are consistent with the assumptions of the EU Reference Scenario in terms of socio-economic developments until 2050. Therefore,
- The differences in terms of economic developments from results of the NEWAGE runs for the GDP and Gross Value Added (GVA) for the industrial sectors are compared and the ratio between the EU Reference Scenario & Base pathway runs is calculated.
- Energy service demand values are not only affected by the economic developments in a country [60, 61]. There are factors such as population growth, efficiency improvements, energy production and transportation of the energy which affect the energy service demand development.
- The effects of the macro-economic development and social effects are assumed equally effective on the demand development.
- As the assumptions are assumed to be consistent for the existing demand figures in TIMES PanEU and the EU Reference Scenario, a factor, 0.5 is applied to reflect the effect of the social development along with the economic growth. According to this, the new demand figures are calculated based on the economic developments from NEWAGE results when only economic developments are taken into account.
- The average of new demand and existing demand figures are taken to calculate the demand figures during the iteration process.
- As there are some differences in terms of the sectoral disaggregation between the models, the sectoral match is required before the iteration process. The sectoral match is applied according to Table 13.

Table 13: The sectoral match between TIMES PanEU and NEWAGE.

TIMES PanEU	NEWAGE
AGR	Agriculture
Commercial Cooling large	Services
Commercial Cooking	Services
Commercial Cooling small	Services
Commercial Heating large	Services
Commercial Heating small	Services
Commercial Lighting	Services
Commercial Other electricity	Services
Commercial Other energy	Services
Commercial Public lighting	Services
Commercial Refrigeration	Services
Commercial Water heat large	Services
Commercial Water heat small	Services
Aluminium	Non-ferrous metal
Ammonia	Chemistry
Other chemical	Chemistry
Chlorine	Chemistry
Cement	Non-metallic minerals
Copper	Non-ferrous metal
Food and Tobacco	Food and Tobacco
Glass Flat	Non-metallic minerals
Glass Hollow	Non-metallic minerals
Iron and Steel	Iron and Steel
Lime	Non-metallic minerals
Other non-ferrous metals	Non-ferrous metal
Other non-metallic minerals	Non-metallic minerals
Other industries	Rest of Industry
High Quality paper	Paper Pulp Print
Non energy consumption chemicals	Chemistry
Non energy consumption others	Non-metallic minerals
Other Sector Consumption	Services
Other electricity	GDP
LKW (Freight)	Transport
Rail Freight	Transport
Aviation (Internal/External)	Transport

Here a summary of the modelling steps for this coupling:

- Energy demands are updated in TIMES PanEU based on results of NEWAGE and the existing demand figures development path for the Base Pathway.
- TIMES PanEU provides the results of the Base pathway to NEWAGE.
- NEWAGE calculates the updated demand growth patterns based on the results of the TIMES PanEU after the data exchange.
- This process shall be repeated until the results of the two models reach equilibrium.

The structure of the data exchange is already established and the first data exchange between the models is ongoing. Few more iterations may be required for the models to reach equilibrium.

4. First application to the REEEM Pathways

The integrated modelling framework as developed in Sections 3.1-3.7. has been applied to the REEEM Base Pathway and two sensitivities called HighRES Pathway and BaseDAM [9] . The Base Pathway narrates a transition towards a low-carbon EU energy system which aims at 80% cut in CO₂ emissions compared to 1990 levels and happens without particular disruptions from current trends. In such pathway, most action towards decarbonisation happens on the supply side and is taken particularly through centralised generation options. The first sensitivity, HighRES Pathway, is collocated in the same future, but it assumes higher renewable generation targets as a mean to achieve decarbonisation. The second sensitivity, instead, assumes policies to internalise the health damage costs of energy-related emissions. In modelling terms, it implements the approach described in Section 3.3. Integration of externalities & damage costs (Link with WP5) , where the health damage costs are embedded in the optimisation function of TIMES PanEU.

The enhancement described in Sections 3.2.3.1 and 3.7. are not incorporated yet, as they are still ongoing as the authors deliver this report.

The main assumptions of these pathways are presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Pathway assumptions.

	Base	BaseDAM	HighRES
GHG ETS	2020 Climate & Energy Package 2030 Climate & Energy Framework 2050:83% - reduction relative to 2005 levels)		
GHG non-ETS	Effort Sharing Decision/Regulation 2050:Country cluster - aiming -75% in EU28)		
Renewable Share targets in the Final Energy Consumption	N.A.	N.A.	Renewable Energy Directive 2050:Country clusters
Damage Costs		Ex-ante	

Figure 7 presents the comparison of the net electricity production figures for the three pathways in the EU28. As explained in Section 2, the electricity supply in this figure includes not only the electricity generation from the public, non-public and CHP power plants but also the net electricity imports.

Figure 7: Net electricity generation in EU28

In Section 3.4., the integration of the updated renewable energy figures and their employment in the model is explained. According to these figures, offshore wind becomes quite competitive with onshore wind and even with Solar PV. Additionally, the availability factor is higher, due to the higher availability of the resource off the coast. With this competitive advantage, offshore wind has relatively high potential and it is chosen over onshore wind and solar technologies especially after 2030 as a mitigation technology which is seen in Figure 7. When the environmental taxes are included in the optimisation function (BaseDAM), higher electricity generation from gas CHP plants is observed in 2030 and 2040 in parallel to the technology deployment of those technologies in Figure 8. The reason for this higher generation in BaseDAM is that the system tries to compensate heat production from the biomass CHP capacities in Base pathway with gas CHP capacities as the biomass is rather polluted energy carrier compared to other gas. Biomass CHP plants have higher ratio of heat produced to electricity produced compared to gas CHP plants. Thereby the higher capacity deployment of the latter is seen in BaseDAM. In the HighRES pathway, nuclear generation is mainly replaced with higher generation from wind and solar. Although the total net generation does not differ significantly between the Base and HighRES pathway, the total capacity

is considerably higher in the HighRES pathway results, due to the high availability factor figures of nuclear compared to renewables. This can be observed in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Net electricity capacity in EU28

Including damage costs in the optimisation function (BaseDAM) leads to similar results in terms of phase out of old coal power plants in the electricity sector after 2030. Additionally, from both Figure 7 and Figure 8, the increase in the net electricity generation in 2050 with respect to 2015 is visible. It is explained by the fact that the rest of the energy system will be electrified. This will bring the requirement for the new infrastructure not only for the E-mobility but also for the unequal and fluctuating electricity capacity from the increase in the share of renewables.

Figure 9: Final Energy Consumption in EU28

The early phase out of coal with the damage costs is visible in Figure 9 as well. In the HighRES pathway, slightly higher shares of electricity and other renewables are observed in the final energy consumption. In the middle term, coal use is mainly compensated with the increase in natural gas use in BaseDAM. The effect of the environmental taxes is visible on the share of biomass in Figure 9 after 2040 in BaseDAM pathway, compared to Base and HighRES pathways.

Figure 10: 2030 ETS Prices in EU28+NO

The effect of the high share of renewables and the damage costs on the ETS prices is shown in Figure 10. As 2030 refers to the middle term of the time horizon, it is chosen to show the impact of additional targets and environmental taxes in the energy system. Damage costs reduce the ETS prices, due to double taxation of coal for the electricity generation. Also the high renewable share target implies lower ETS prices, compared to Base pathway because of deployment of additional mitigation technologies in the system.

5. Outlook

The REEEM project investigates the usefulness of an integrated assessment modelling framework to gain comprehensive understanding of the system-wide implications of the European energy system transition towards to a low carbon society. The aim of the study is to extend the traditional scope of existing integrated assessment models to a wider set of impact assessments across society, economy and environment.

In this report, the development of such framework and its final features were described, with distinction by sector. The modelling tools and methodologies developed for each sectorial assessment were presented, along with the steps taken to link the insights to those obtained by TIMES PanEU energy model. The main steps of the development are here summarised:

1. *Technology innovation outlooks* developed in Technology Innovation Roadmaps are integrated, with focus on storage options, renewable energy technologies and heat savings in residential buildings.
2. An assessment of the *health impacts of emissions* by the energy sector is carried out. For this purpose, a soft-link is established between TIMES PanEU and EcoSense.
3. A step is moved into accounting for *regional and local specificities of the energy system development* of selected EU countries. This part builds on a harmonisation process between TIMES PanEU and case study models focusing on energy supply security and grid and dispatch with the help of the experts in the case study regions, existing base year capacities and electricity trade flow between the regions are improved and the planned capacities from the ENTSO-E reports are incorporated in the model as well.
4. A first step is marked into the inclusion of *impacts of consumers' technology choices* onto the achievement of decarbonisation targets in the whole EU. The main drivers of consumers' choices regarding heating and transportation are drawn from surveys through a novel discrete choice model. Selected insights are included in TIMES PanEU.
5. The *effect of climate changes on heating and cooling demand* across the EU is evaluated starting from climate databases. In turn, the effect of these changes on the energy demand-supply balance and investment requirements is assessed through TIMES PanEU.
6. Finally, economic impacts of the energy transition are integrated to TIMES PanEU with a soft-link with NEWAGE.

During the development of the integrated assessment modelling framework, discrepancies between results of parallel assessments emerged. Specifically, the storage capacity deployment resulting from TIMES PanEU is limited, compared to the outlook provided by the relevant Technology Innovation Roadmap. This is believed to be due to the lower temporal resolution of the energy system model. The deployment of the storage technologies shall be further investigated with higher temporal resolution models or with an electricity market model to discuss their role in the energy transition.

The implementation of the consumers' behaviour in an EU-scale energy system optimisation model is another challenging task, as the service demand categories are not differentiated according to consumers' decision drivers such as age, income group, education level. The effect of these drivers can be further investigated with the disaggregation of the demand services in future studies.

Damage costs due to different pollutants are assessed in the framework, but sectoral disaggregation is not applied yet. Their effect on the system can be also assessed with sectoral differentiation of the cost figures. In this way, synergies between pollutant mitigation and GHG emission reduction scenarios can be investigated at the sectoral level.

The development of the modelling framework is still ongoing. The incorporation of the heat saving measures and the coupling between NEWAGE and the energy system model are scheduled as last steps in the integrated modelling framework. In this context, the damage costs calculations realised by another health impact assessment model, EVA, will be integrated into TIMES PanEU as well and the results will be compared with the TIMES PanEU – EcoSense framework as sensitivity analyses.

After finalising the development, the full integrated modelling framework will be run for all the pathways structured within REEEM. Sensitivity analyses will be carried out to evaluate the robustness of the results and the pathways will be compared with each other to understand the impacts of different storylines and drivers. The results will be further analysed as well, to assess how different targets or availability of different technologies create differences on the results for the energy transition in Europe. These analyses and the key messages drawn from all the modeling activities with the integrated assessment model will be detailed in D1.2b 'Second Integrated Impact report'. In this deliverable, the results will be elaborated on and the impacts of the different drivers in the energy system transition will be discussed.

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